

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 4.2, 1st Annual standardisation recommendations Public

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Summary

This Deliverable D4.2 was developed in Task 4.3 and details recommendations for standardization in the field of Digital Forensics with a special focus on Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies.

Introduction

WP4 Overview

Work Package 4 is divided in the following tasks:

Task 4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference

The aim of this task is to develop WP4's Terms of Reference, defining in detail:

- The standardisation state of the art in the area of fighting cybercrime: identifying relevant CEN/CENELEC/ISO technical committees, related projects and other national and international activities. Determining the relevant stakeholders and highlighting persons in law enforcement interested in the topic (within consortium partners and the wider CYCLOPES LEA Community). Agreeing on the structure for WP4 standardisation reports.
- Innovation uptake state of the art in the security area: identification of current legal regulations, frameworks and best practices providing LEAs with an effective procurement approach for innovative solutions. Recognising the relevant stakeholders and persons in law enforcement that are interested in this topic.

The present Deliverable D4.1 contains WP4's Terms of Reference.

Task 4.2 Standardisation recommendations

Partners involved in this will participate in the practitioners' workshops, facilitating one-hour discussions dedicated to previous experiences related to standardisation, expectations, priorities and needs in this area. Combining information gathered from the practitioners' workshops with ongoing analyses of current and forthcoming works conducted by standardisation bodies will be a baseline for the series of annual reports on standardisation recommendations.

Task 4.3 Annual standardisation workshops

Based on information gathered within task 4.2, CYCLOPES will choose at least one topic, which will be further elaborated during a dedicated yearly workshop. Workshops will be organised independently, or in cooperation with particular technical committees' workshops or conferences. The ambition is to promote standardisation as an effective tool in the fight against cybercrime, while exploring the opportunities to streamline processes and procedures that will maintain efficacy and maximise effectiveness. The inputs gathered from the participants during the yearly workshops will be summarized in the reports that constitute the Deliverable 4.2 Annual standardization recommendations.

Task 4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations

Innovation uptake is a process, starting from the elicitation of the specific needs of users, utilising the most appropriate innovation procurement model for the demand, and then ensuring the greatest impact of a new innovation – with a specific testing, validation and improvement loop. In this task, we will gather and collate existing frameworks, best practices and guidelines for innovation uptake in the Security area, along with the outcomes in WP3. Other activities in this task include the assimilation of key aspects of the materials gathered; providing recommendations for LEAs on the most congruent approach for cybercrime innovation uptake.

WP4 Objectives

WP4 has two main objectives:

- 1) to identify priorities related to fighting cybercrime which require more standardisation;
- 2) to develop recommendations, facilitating and fostering cybercrime innovation uptake in LEAs.

WP4 will contribute to the overall CYCLOPES project Objective 4:

Ob 4. To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake

4.1 To define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

Related KPI: An annual report providing recommendations for standardisation will be delivered. The composition of these reports will create a standardisation roadmap.

Methods of measurement: Tasks 4.2, 4.3 and deliverable D4.2.

4.2 To provide a roadmap with recommendations to LEAs for the effective (also cost-efficient) innovation uptake, based on identified experiences, best practices, legal regulations and EU/national financial and organisational incentives for innovation uptake.

Related KPI: One annual report with recommendations on innovation uptake will be prepared. The innovation uptake roadmap will be a composition of all 5 reports.

Methods of measurement: Task 4.4 and deliverable D4.3.

WP4 Deliverables

D4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference (M06)

D4.2 1st Annual standardisation recommendations (M12)

D4.3 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations (M24)

D4.4 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations (M36)

D4.5 4th Annual standardisation recommendations (M48)

D4.2 1st Annual standardisation recommendations

D4.6 5th Annual standardisation recommendations (M60)

D4.7 1st Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M12)

D4.8 2nd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M24)

D4.9 3rd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M36)

D4.10 4th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M48)

D4.11 5th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M60)

WP4 Partners

CYCLOPES partners participating in the individual tasks of WP4 are presented in table 1.

Table 1 CYCLOPES partners' involvement in WP4 tasks

Partner Acronym	Partner full name	T4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference	T4.2 Standardisation recommendations	T4.3 Annual standardisation workshops	T4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations
ASI	Austrian Standards International	X	X	X	
BFP	Police Federale Belge			X	X
CPEB	College of Policing Limited, United Kingdom	X	X	X	X
DITSS	Stichting Dutch Institute for Technology, Safety & Security				X
GDCOC	Glavna Direktsia Borba S Organiziranata Prestupnost			X	X
GUCI	Ministerio del Interior, Spain			X	X
HO	Home Office United Kingdom			X	X
IANUS	IANUS Consulting Ltd.				X
KWPG	Provincial Police Headquarters in Gdansk			X	X
MPF	Malta Police Force			X	X
MUP	Ministry of Interior, Croatia			X	X
NPN	The National Police of the Netherlands			X	X
PPHS	Polish Platform for Homeland Security	X	X	X	X
SPA	Polismyndigheten Swedish Policy Authority	X	X	X	X
SPLV	Iekšlietu Ministrijas Valsts Policija State Police of the Ministry of Interior, Latvia			X	X
ZITIS	Zentrale Stelle für Informationstechnik im Sicherheitsbereich	X	X	X	X

1. Selected Topic

On 15. December 2021 WP2, Identification of practitioners' capabilities, gaps and requirements, organized a workshop in the area of Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies.

Mobile devices and Wearable Technologies, especially smartphones and fitness trackers represent a unique challenge for law enforcement. Due to their wide use, they underpin many criminal investigations. For instance, one may find critical evidence in a smartphone of a victim who is in no position to unlock the device. Moreover, criminal offenders, organised crime and terrorist organisations use mobile devices for various purposes, which introduces many challenges for criminal prosecution. Determining how the data got onto the mobile device is not always simple as these devices often sync and share data with other digital media and cloud services. Law enforcement need not only to access the data stored on mobile devices, but also provide it as court evidence in a trustworthy and reliable manner.

Practitioners' needs expressed in two other workshops organised within WP2:

- "Remote Desktop Protocols and similar technologies" that was held on 10th – 11th February 2022 in Gdansk (Poland), and
- "Social Engineering to enable Cybercrime" that was held on 30th – 31st March 2022 in Stockholm (Sweden)

will be subject to the 2nd Deliverable of T4.3, i.e. D4.3.

1.1. State of the art in the selected topic

Applying the methodology specified in D4.1 for the area of Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies the following standardization committees were identified together with related standardization activities:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 40, IT service management and IT governance:
 - o [ISO/IEC 30121:2015](#), Information technology — Governance of digital forensic risk framework
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection:
 - o [ISO/IEC 27037:2012](#), Information technology — Security techniques — Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence
 - o [ISO/IEC 27041:2015](#), Information technology — Security techniques — Guidance on assuring suitability and adequacy of incident investigative method
 - o [ISO/IEC 27042:2015](#), Information technology — Security techniques — Guidelines for the analysis and interpretation of digital evidence
 - o [ISO/IEC 27043:2015](#), Information technology — Security techniques — Incident investigation principles and processes

- [ISO/IEC 27050](#) (all parts), Information technology — Security techniques — Electronic discovery
- IEC/TC 124, Wearable electronic devices and technologies:
 - No forensic specific activities because the focus of the TC's work program is on product characteristics.
- CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, Cybersecurity and Data Protection: The following European Standards are elaborated under the Vienna Agreement between CEN and ISO, i.e. transposition of ISO Standards into European Standards collection.
 - EN ISO/IEC 27037:2016, Information technology - Security techniques - Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence (ISO/IEC 27037:2012)
 - EN ISO/IEC 27041:2016, Information technology - Security techniques - Guidance on assuring suitability and adequacy of incident investigative method (ISO/IEC 27041:2015)
 - EN ISO/IEC 27042:2016, Information technology - Security techniques - Guidelines for the analysis and interpretation of digital evidence (ISO/IEC 27042:2015)
 - EN ISO/IEC 27043:2016, Information technology - Security techniques - Incident investigation principles and processes (ISO/IEC 27043:2015)
- CEN Workshop FORMOBILE:
 - [CWA 17865:2022](#), Requirements and Guidelines for a complete end-to-end mobile forensic investigation chain
- Cyber-investigation Analysis Standard Expression (CASE, <https://caseontology.org/>):
 - CASE is a community-developed evolving standard that provides a structured (ontology-based) specification for representing information commonly analyzed and exchanged by people and systems during investigations involving digital evidence. CASE ensures that analysis results can be traced back to their source(s), keeping track of when, where and who used which tools to perform investigative actions on data sources.

The following EU policies are related to the selected topic:

- The Council of Europe. (2001). Convention on Cybercrime. Budapest: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/185>
- Directive 2012/13/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 on the right to information in criminal proceedings
- Directive 2014/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters
- Directive (EU) 2016/343 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on the strengthening of certain aspects of the presumption of innocence and of the right to be present at the trial in criminal proceedings

- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

2. Practitioners' needs

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop in the area of Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies and collected the following needs expressed by practitioners. These needs were assessed regarding how these needs can be met by standardization.

- 1) Practitioners from Belgium expressed the need for the **development of a forensic standard for mobile device acquisition**. The participants expressed a need for standard operation procedures and guidelines regarding the mobile device acquisition. Quite often, the first responders do not have the (legal) possibility or time to seize or capture a complete system, so they need to perform a triage on the existing possibilities.

(Accredited) Forensic laboratory use [ISO/IEC 17025:2017](#), General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories. But this International Standard is very generic and doesn't provide specific requirements and guidelines for digital forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies.

See Sub-Clause 3.1.

- 2) Practitioners from Belgium and Estonia expressed the needs **to know how (commercial) tools work**, to assure they won't alter relevant data, and for documentation respectively description of forensic tools, i.e. their data extraction methods are working, what data they alter. User of forensic tools often need to know how the tools work to be able to assure the usage will not alter (relevant) data. There is a need that either the methods and procedures are documented and testable or the tool vendors can reliably assure data will not be altered during extraction or analysis.

See Sub-Clause **Error! Reference source not found.**

- 3) Practitioners from Estonia, Poland, Kosovo, Spain, United Kingdom and Latvia expressed the need for a **unified reporting system** in order to facilitate the exchange and fusion of extracted data/images, (customizable) tool reports as well as the remote analysis of forensic cases case.

See Sub-Clause 3.3.

- 4) Practitioners from Belgium and Latvia expressed the need for Standards defining the use of **Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning in forensic cases**, incl. requirements for usage and assertions for not altering data.

See Sub-Clause 3.4.

Considering the needs expressed by practitioners in the WP2 Workshop, assessed by T8.2 and having identified those standardization committees with which these needs can be discussed to elaborate recommendations on standardization, the following standardization committees were contacted by T8.3 Lead (ASI):

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
- CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, Cybersecurity and Data Protection
- CEN Workshop FORMOBILE
- Cyber-investigation Analysis Standard Expression (CASE)

Representatives from these standardization committees were invited to a standardization workshop, which were hold online on 8. March 2022, in order to:

- indicate priorities regarding domains requiring (further) standardisation
- define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

Next to standardization representatives the following CYCLOPES partners attended the workshop: ASI, BFP, CPEB, GUCI, KWPG, PPHS and ZITIS.

3. Recommendations on standardization

3.1. Development of a forensic standard for mobile device acquisition

In the standardization workshop the need for standardisation for device- and data acquisitions was discussed and as highly relevant confirmed. But it has to be taken into consideration that seizing the device and acquiring the data – data stored on the mobile phone and data in the cloud – are two different issues with differing legal and ethical challenges. There is also the need for having guidelines for the handling of cryptophones, due to the special decryption of these devices.

LEAs emphasised that for such a forensic standard for mobile device acquisition it should be a framework standard, laying out principles to be used as a basis for standard operating procedures, which define the further practical details.

The representative from the CEN Workshop FORMOBILE reported, that for meeting these needs the CEN Workshop Agreement CWA 17865:2022, Requirements and Guidelines for a complete end-to-end mobile forensic investigation chain, was elaborated. This CWA focuses on the Personnel, Tools, Processes and Legal and Ethical framework specific for mobile forensics and including competencies, device seizure, data preservation, data acquisition, data

examination and analysis, documentation of all investigation steps, reporting, evaluation and sharing of information with other LEAs, and legal and ethical considerations.

Taking advantage of ISO standards from ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC 27, this CWA 17865 offers a collection of building blocks covering different aspects of mobile forensics allowing for adjustments based on national laws and regulations as well as internal rules and codes of conduct. It allows LEAs from different countries to accommodate their available technical solutions, at the same time offering a standardised collection of procedures and requirements.

The representative from the CEN Workshop FORMOBILE informed, that CWA 17865 will be published mid of March and will be publicly available for download from <https://www.cenelec.eu/get-involved/research-and-innovation/cen-and-cenelec-activities/cwa-download-area/>.

3.2. Assurance of tools used in digital/mobile forensic

Partners attended the workshop underlined that standards for testing and validation of forensics tools are needed in order to present evidence at the court in a reliable and trusted way. Especially standards for validation of results are needed. It has to be assured that generated information is based on the provided real data, acquired data was not altered and results are also reproducible by third parties. Currently every LEA is doing their own testing, which makes direct comparisons with other LEAs almost impossible. In certain cases, examinations rely on individual experts instead of on a standard elaborated and accepted by the market.

Existing standards like ISO/IEC 27037, ISO/IEC 27041, ISO/IEC 27042 or ISO/IEC 27043 dealing with this need on a process level. It was recognized in the workshop, that digital/mobile forensics is a fast-moving and rapidly evolving scientific area and for that reason, it is difficult to produce a set of standards with sufficient detail to be relevant, whilst simultaneously being flexible enough to remain valid for the long term. That makes the elaboration of a standard for mobile forensics tools very challenging and even unproductive.

Referring to this, the representative from the CEN Workshop FORMOBILE informed that CWA 17865 describes good practice and guidance for the selection and use of mobile forensic tools within the wider guidance of this document for personnel and processes in a dedicated Clause 6 on Tools. Additionally, this CWA provides a quick overview of points in different Annexes to consider when selecting a mobile forensic tool.

In further discussion under this item the additional need for a having a European centralised independent test body available for tool testing was addressed. This was also an outcome of the discussion in the FORMOBILE project, which is the driver of the CWA 17865. Such European body, like the US National Institute for Science and Technology (NIST), could be of benefit for all users to test and validate digital/mobile forensic tools to certify these products.

3.3. Unified reporting system

All tools in digital/mobile forensics offer reasonable reporting systems, but there are no "standardized" interfaces between them. Solving this challenge aids in the verification of data

that has been extracted using different forensic tools and allows for easier and clearer results comparisons.

This issue is addressed by CASE (Cyber-investigation Analysis Standard Expression) providing *"an extension of the Unified Cyber Ontology (UCO), which defines classes of cyber objects (e.g., items, tools, people, places), the relations to other cyber objects, provenance of items and actions taken in an action life-cycle. The CASE domain of discourse is focused on "investigation" concentrated on Observable Objects and their associated Facets, whereas the UCO serves as an ontological foundation for modeling the broader cyber-domain, treating observable cyber-items and their associated facets more generally. Developers of systems and tools used in cyber-investigations are working to export information in CASE format to allow automated normalization, combination, correlation, and validation of information, which means less time extracting and combining data, and more time analyzing information."*¹

CWA 17865 refers to CASE in Clause 6.7 on Tool interoperability requiring that tools selected for mobile forensics should, wherever possible, support the concept of openness in terms of data exchange between other forensic tools and support standard industry file formats.

3.4. Standards defining AI/ML usage in forensic cases

Even there are ongoing standardization activities on European and international level for Artificial Intelligence and Machine-Learning (e.g. in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, Artificial intelligence, and CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21, Artificial Intelligence) there is no specific activity supporting the use of such technologies in forensic examinations. It was stated, that routine procedures can be performed by AI but in certain cases human elements (supervision) will always be needed to ensure important ethical and societal aspect are considered and followed. Furthermore, the use of AI in court trial processes, incl. forensics, will be subject to the forthcoming Artificial Intelligence Act of the European Union because such instances may be qualified as high-risk AI systems.

Information about governance implications of the use of Artificial Intelligence in mobile/digital forensics is provided in Annex F of CWA 17865. But the representative of the CEN Workshop FORMOBILE explained that Artificial Intelligence was not in the focus of this European Standardization deliverable.

The standardization workshop concluded and clearly recommended that further research and standardization for defining the use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine-Learning in forensic examination is needed.

¹ See <https://caseontology.org/ontology/intro.html>

4. List of stakeholders

In the area of Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies the following stakeholders were identified:

- National LEAs,
- Europol,
- The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- EU Agency for law enforcement training (CEPOL),
- EC DG HOME,
- EC DG JUST,
- Interpol²,
- Forensic laboratories,
- Forensic Tool vendors,
- Legal and ethical advisors,
- Prosecutors,
- Defence attorneys,
- Judges,
- Ministries of justice,
- EU-funded research projects, e.g.
 - o AIDA, Artificial Intelligence and advanced Data Analytics for Law Enforcement Agencies
 - o EXFILES, Extract Forensic Information for LEAs from Encrypted SmartPhones
 - o FORMOBILE, From mobile phones to court – A complete FORensic investigation chain targeting MOBILE devices
 - o ILEAnet, Innovation by Law Enforcement Agencies networking,
 - o INSPECTr, Intelligence Network and Secure Platform for Evidence Correlation and Transfer
 - o LOCARD, Lawful evidence collecting and continuity platform development

² See e.g. INTERPOL (2021). Guidelines for digital Forensics – First responders - Best practices for search and seizure of electronic and digital evidence

https://www.interpol.int/content/download/16243/file/Guidelines%20to%20Digital%20Forensics%20First%20Responders_V7.pdf

5. Follow-up of and update for recommendations from previous reporting periods

Since this is the first report of Task 4.3, there is neither any follow-up of nor any update for recommendations from previous reporting periods.

Conclusion

Needs expressed by practitioners in the CYCLOPES WP2 workshop regarding Digital Forensics of Mobile Devices and Wearable Technologies and standardization were adequately addressed and discussed with representatives from standardization communities. Most of these needs are already met in existing standards. These needs are those for a forensic standard for mobile device and data acquisition, the assurance of tools used in digital/mobile forensic and a unified reporting system ensuring interoperability and data exchange between tools and systems from different vendors. The reason these needs emerged is due to that LEAs were not aware of the standards available respectively the just recently published CWA 17865. This is a clear recommendation, that standardization organisations should put more effort in engaging with stakeholders next to those who already participate in the drafting of these standards, especially LEAs, and making them aware on the solutions provided in those standards.

Regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine-Learning in mobile/digital forensic further research and standardization is needed.

Annex A: Standardization overview

In ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004³), 1.1 standardization is defined as an activity of establishing, with regard to actual or potential problems, provisions for common and repeated use, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Important benefits of standardization are improvement of the suitability of products, processes and services for their intended purposes, prevention of barriers to trade and facilitation of technological cooperation. Standardization supports the social and economic development by ensuring safety, quality and competitiveness of products, services, and processes on various levels (e. g. performance, composition, interoperability, applicability and many more). This in turn supports economic activity of businesses of all sizes and allows them access markets all over the world.

Standardization is governed by the principles of consensus, openness, inclusiveness transparency, national commitment and coherence as outlined in the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade of the World Trade Organisation (WTO TBT Agreement) and in Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation.

The output of standardization are standards. According to ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, 3.1 a standard is a document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Standards are voluntary in their application and should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology, and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits. Standards are initiated and drafted by stakeholders such as industry, incl. SMEs, public authorities, research organisations, societal and environmental stakeholders, consumer organisations, trade unions and conformity assessment bodies.

There are numerous organizations developing standards, ranging from companies, consortia and industry in the private sector, to national, regional and international organizations. The latter three constitute the bulk of the international standardization system, required by the WTO TBT Agreement to follow its principles and requirements for standards development. There are also NGOs with specific socio-economic or environmental goals that develop and publish standards.

National Standardization Bodies (NSB) are standardization organizations located in each country. They bridge the local communities with groups of relevant stakeholders outside of their country and represent the pillars of the European and International standardization. Being member of European Standardization Organisations NSBs are obliged to implement European Standards as national standards and withdraw any conflicting national standards.

The European standardization activities are conducted within the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

CEN brings together the national standardization bodies of 34 European countries and provides a platform for standardization in various areas, including products, materials, services, and processes. CENELEC ensures standardisation in the electro-technical

³ ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, Standardization and related activities — General vocabulary, is adopted in Europe as European Standard EN 45020:2006.

engineering field, and ETSI produces standards for information and communications technology.

The network of European standardization includes more than 200.000 experts from different countries and from the different stakeholders, i. e. business, industry and commerce, service providers, consumers, environmental and societal organisations, public authorities, and regulators, as well as other public and private institutions. The European Standardization Organisations aim to support needs of the market and of different stakeholders, promoting the European Standardization System and leading the implementation of best practice in standardization around the world. They collaborate with key stakeholders' organisations at national, European and international level, support international Standardization and cooperate closely with international Standardization Organisation such as ISO and IEC. Participation in European Standardization follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of European Standards.

International standardization activities are conducted at three major international Standardization Organisation: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU).

ISO is an independent international organization that includes 165 national standards bodies as its members. International standards, produced by ISO, cover a wide variety of areas and represent consensus of experts from many countries. All CEN members are also members of ISO.

Members of IEC are 89 National Committees, represented by delegates from industry, research and government bodies of each country. IEC produces standards covering all aspects of production and use of electrical and electronic devices and systems. All CENELEC members are also members of IEC.

CEN and CENELEC have dedicated agreements with the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), promoting the benefits of the international standards to international trade and markets harmonization. The high level of convergence between the European and international standards is facilitated by the ongoing technical cooperation between CEN and ISO (Vienna Agreement) and between CENELEC and IEC (Frankfurt Agreement). The main objectives of these agreements are to provide a:

- framework for the optimal use of resources and expertise available for standardization work;
- mechanism for information exchange between international and European Standardization Organizations to increase the transparency of ongoing work at international and European levels.

International Standards from ISO and IEC following the Vienna or Frankfurt Agreement become the status of European Standards (designation EN ISO, EN ISO/IEC, EN IEC).

ITU is an inter-governmental organization belonging to the United Nations and develops technical standards that facilitate the use of public telecommunication services and systems for communications in the area of ICT. Its membership comprises nearly 200 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions.

Participation in International Standardization of ISO and IEC follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of International Standards.

A vast array of normative documents is classed under the generic label of "private standards". Generally, a normative document developed and published by an organization outside of the recognized standards development organizations at national, regional, or international level is considered to be a private standard. There is not only a vast range of private standards (and growing in number), but there are also significant differences between the bodies and organizations that develop these standards related to such aspects as governance, development approach, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and consensus.

Some of these Private Standards Development Organisations liaise with recognized standards development organizations. Such examples are IEEE and ENISA liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection or OASIS liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 2, Biometric technical interfaces. Some specifications from Private Standards Development Organisations were provided by them to recognized standards development organizations to be implemented as standards.

Another aspect to consider is how standardization bodies deal with intellectual property in standards. In many sectors of the economy, companies make significant financial and human investments in the development of new technologies and products. As a result, the best available technology that experts want to include in a standard is often protected by one or more patents. This is especially true in certain areas where interoperable and complex technologies cause standard developers to consider new and emerging technologies that are normally protected by patents. These contributions may contain patented technologies which are commonly known as Standard Essential Patents (SEP). When it is not possible on technical grounds to make or operate equipment or methods which comply with a standard without infringing a SEP, i. e. without using technologies that are covered by one or more patents, the patent is described as being 'essential' for the application of the standard. To preserve the universal approach of standards, while also respecting the rights of the patent holders, ISO, IEC, ITU, CEN, CENELEC and ETSI have developed an intellectual property rights (IPR) policy. In brief, this policy encourages the early disclosure and identification of patents that may relate to standards under development. The IPR Policy provides for the incorporation of patented technology into new standards, on condition that the IPR holder is ready to allow this either without financial compensation or at Fair, Reasonable and non-Discriminatory (FRAND) conditions to other standard users.

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